

An Evaluation of Efficacy of Automated Blood Culture System of Dg Technology Using Bact/Alert 3d 60.

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Conflict of interest: DG Technology provided automated blood culture system and blood culture bottles of both the manufacturers.

Abstract:

Introduction: Sepsis is a potentially deadly medical condition characterized by a whole body inflammatory state due to a variety of pathogenic organisms in blood. Early diagnosis and initiation of proper antibiotic therapy by performing blood culture tests is of prime importance. Conventional blood culture method has some limitations, like prolonged time of reporting. Automated Blood Culture techniques for microbiological diagnosis of sepsis is more commonly used in comparison to conventional blood culture methods as it continuously monitors blood culture systems with faster turnaround time. This study was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of the automated blood culture system of DG Technologies by comparing it with BacT/ALERT 3D 60.

Material and Method: This study was conducted at department of microbiology, C U Shah Medical College, Surendranagar. Total seven organisms in different concentrations i.e 10, 10² and 10⁴ CFU/ml were prepared and 1 ml suspension from each dilution was inoculated in aerobic blood culture bottles of both the manufacturers. Sterile whole blood in quantity of 5 ml was added in all the bottles to check the efficacy of blood culture media to neutralize the antimicrobial effect of the blood.

Result: Both the system showed similar outcome for all seven organisms and for all three concentrations i.e 10, 10² and 10⁴ CFU/ml. A minor difference in turnaround time was noted. The difference in time ranges from 10 to 30 min.

Conclusion: The DG Technology automated blood culture system gives quite comparable results with the standard existing automated system (BacT/ALERT 3D 60).

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Introduction

Sepsis is a deadly medical condition characterized by whole body inflammatory state which is due to variety of pathogenic organisms in blood. [1] Early diagnosis and initiation of proper antibiotic therapy of bloodstream infections (BSI) initially is of prime importance. [2] Traditionally, diagnosing sepsis relied on manual blood culture methods, which were time-consuming and could delay the initiation of appropriate treatment. However, with advancements in medical technology, automated blood culture systems have revolutionized the diagnostic process. Automated Blood Culture techniques for microbiological diagnosis of sepsis

is more useful compared to conventional blood culture method due to its less turnaround time. [3]

A broad spectrum of bacterial pathogens, encompassing both gram-positive and gram-negative varieties, has been identified as culprits for septicaemia. Gram-negative sepsis is often linked with a comparatively higher mortality rate compared to gram-positive counterparts. In developing nations, the identification of bacterial pathogens is frequently hindered by inadequate laboratory techniques and a scarcity of technical proficiency. Despite the recent progress in diagnostic molecular techniques for sepsis microbiological diagnosis, conventional blood

culture remains the widely accepted gold standard. [4]

The BacT/ALERT 3D 60 system operates by detecting microbial growth through the monitoring of changes in CO₂ concentration as microorganisms proliferate within blood culture bottles. [5]

Automated BacT/ALERT 3D 60 system can prove to be a new hope for the clinicians for the diagnosis of septicaemia among patients as it continuously monitors blood culture systems with faster turnaround time. Current study is conducted to evaluate sensitivity and turnaround time of novel automated blood culture system (DG Technologies) which works on the same principle as BacT/ALERT 3D 60.

Material and Method

This study was conducted at the Department of Microbiology, C.U. Shah Medical College, Surendranagar, Gujarat. New automated blood culture system i.e. DG Technology was compared with the existing standard automated blood culture system i.e. BacT/ALERT 3D 60 for parameters like turnaround time and sensitivity.

The BacT/ALERT 3D 60 bottles are composed of 40 ml of tryptic soy broth, along with 0.035% sodium polyanetholesulfonate, and are supplemented with various additives tailored for either the aerobic or anaerobic medium. On the

other hand, the Signal bottles contain 70 ml of supplemented tryptic soy broth and 0.03% sodium polyanethole sulfonate. [6]

The proprietary media utilized in the system are formulated from a tryptic soy broth, enriched with complex amino acids and carbohydrates. These components are meticulously redesigned to facilitate growth while ensuring optimal production of CO₂. Each bottle is equipped with a CO₂ sensor affixed to its bottom, separated from the broth medium by a semipermeable membrane. This membrane selectively allows CO₂ to pass through while maintaining impermeability to water. The BacT/ALERT 3D 60 system conducts CO₂ production tests in each bottle a total of 144 times per day. The resulting data points, plotted as reflectance units over time, generate a growth curve for analysis. [7]

Total seven organisms i.e. *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella Typhi* and *Candida albicans* in different concentration i.e. 10, 10² and 10⁴ CFU/ml were prepared and 1 ml of suspension from each dilution was inoculated in aerobic blood culture bottle of both the manufacturer as per standard protocol. Sterile whole human blood in quantity of 5 ml was added in all the bottles to check the efficacy of blood culture media to neutralize the antimicrobial effect of the human blood.

Figure 1: BacT/ALERT 3D 60 system

Figure 2: Automated Blood culture bottles

Figure 3: DG Technologies system

Result

The DG Technology automated blood culture system demonstrated an impressive sensitivity of 100% as all the blood cultures incubated in the

system were flagged positive. This indicates a high level of accuracy in detecting the presence of organisms in the blood samples, highlighting the reliability of the technology with given batch of blood culture bottles.

Graph 1: Shows mean time (min) of test positivity for different organisms and concentration

A notable contrast between the two systems emerged in the significantly higher rate of *Candida albicans* recovery observed in The DG Technology automated blood culture system compared to the BacT/ALERT 3D 60 automated blood culture system. This discrepancy, as illustrated in Table 1,

stands in contrast to the findings of the study conducted by Smith et al. [8]

The other findings were found to be almost similar with the study done by Smith et al. as shown in table:-1.

Table 1: Shows Time of detection(hr) of positive flagged Blood culture bottle.

Organisms with different concentration	Our study DG Technology (hr)	Smith at el, ⁸ BacT/ALERT (hr)
E.coli 10	16.08	13.39
E.coli 10 ²	11.13	-
E.coli 10 ⁴	8.9	-
S.aureus 10	18.46	18.80
S.aureus 10 ²	15.83	-
S.aureus 10 ⁴	12.31	-
A.baumannii 10	12.21	15.50
A.baumannii 10 ²	11.38	-
A.baumannii 10 ⁴	8.7	-
K. pneumoniae 10	18.51	12.66
K. pneumoniae 10 ²	16.43	-
K. pneumoniae 10 ⁴	12.55	-
S.Typhi 10	13.1	-
S.Typhi 10 ²	10.65	-
S.Typhi 10 ⁴	7.2	-
C. albicans 10	18.03	31.46
C. albicans 10 ²	15.71	-
C. albicans 10 ⁴	10.76	-
P. aeruginosa 10	21.7	14.70
P. aeruginosa 10 ²	12.85	-
P. aeruginosa 10 ⁴	11.08	-

Throughout the study period, the software programs associated with DG Technology did not perform satisfactorily. One notable complaint raised by technologists pertained to the audible alarm signaling a positive culture within DG Technology systems. Many staff members found these alarms highly bothersome, as they interfered with their other responsibilities. However, it was acknowledged that this issue could be rectified with a software update.

Calculating and comparing the time intervals for detection in both systems was deemed crucial. However, it's essential to acknowledge the possibility of inherent differences in the growth capabilities of DG Technology resins and the standard media used in BacT/ALERT 3D 60. Furthermore, it's noteworthy that the growth patterns of bacteria and fungi were quite similar in both systems, indicating satisfactory growth capabilities of both media.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, the DG Technology Automated Blood Culture System demonstrated commendable attributes, being both compact and user-friendly. This technological advancement in blood culture systems presents a promising solution for efficient and user-intuitive laboratory practices. The evaluation of its sensitivity, conducted with seven different organisms, showcased results that were statistically comparable to those obtained with the well-established BacT/ALERT 3D 60 system. This finding is particularly significant as it underscores

the reliability of the DG Technology system in accurately identifying positive blood cultures across various microbial strains.

Furthermore, the study delved into the critical aspect of turnaround time, comparing the DG Technology system with the BacT/ALERT 3D 60. The analysis revealed that the turnaround time of the DG Technology system was statistically similar to that of the BacT/ALERT 3D 60. This parity in turnaround time suggests that the DG Technology system not only matches the sensitivity of the BacT/ALERT 3D 60 but also maintains efficiency in providing timely results. These results collectively highlight the potential of the DG Technology Automated Blood Culture System to be a valuable asset in clinical laboratories, offering a user-friendly interface, comparable sensitivity to established systems, and competitive turnaround times for improved patient care and laboratory workflow.

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